

WEGDYN-AT model documentation

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Summary

This document gives a thorough documentation of the WEGDYN-AT computable general equilibrium (CGE) model. WEGDYN-AT is a model of Austria's economy, which is tailored for the analysis of the economy-wide and macroeconomic effects of climate policy. The model depicts Austria's economy as a relatively large number of economic sectors (81) and households (13), which are connected via input-output relations. This means that all sectors or households are either directly or indirectly connected with each other via their respective demand/cost structures. The model thus allows for analyzing indirect effects that are triggered by interventions in the economic system of Austria. WEGDYN-AT is calibrated to 2014 and solved in a recursive dynamic fashion until 2050. The model represents the most relevant technologies and behavioral structures from the perspective of climate change mitigation. Special features are the high resolution regarding the energy sector, with multiple electricity and heat generation technologies as well as co-generation. Also, the transport sector is resolved at high detail, with processes within the sector such as motorized individual transport, public transport, freight transport and transport infrastructure provision being explicitly modelled in terms of production functions. Special emphasis is placed on the production of basic metals, since the steel sectors is a major emitter of greenhouse gas emissions in Austria. Further, due to the high number of private households, differentiated between three residence locations (urban, sub-urban and periphery) and income quartiles, the analysis of distributional effects of climate change mitigation is possible. Finally, since the government is explicitly represented as a separate household, the fiscal effects as well as interactions between the private and the public sector can be analyzed.

This documentation is structured as follows: Chapter 1 provides a non-technical model description, including an illustration of the model in terms of nesting trees. Chapter 2 gives a comprehensive mathematical model formulation. It first introduces a general notation, followed by equations for the three main CGE conditions of "zero profit", "market clearance" and "income balance". Chapter 3 describes the recursive dynamics of the model as well as how the economy grows. Chapter 4 provides detailed information on the data that is used to calibrate the model.

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1. Non-technical model description

1.1. General overview

WEGDYN-AT is a computable general equilibrium (CGE) model of Austria's economy. A CGE model depicts an economy as a whole in terms of annual monetary flows across sectors and agents. These flows are assumed to be in a flow-equilibrium. More precisely, the long-term assumption of general equilibrium is implemented, meaning that all markets are cleared simultaneously (supply equals demand on all markets) and additionally long-term macroeconomic balances hold. Within this macro-economic balancing framework, economic agents are assumed to behave according to microeconomic principles of cost minimization and utility maximization. Hence, actors are flexible subject to their pre-specified production and consumption functions, meaning that they can react to price changes by altering their demand for goods, however restricted by budgetary, technological as well as supply constraints.

When calibrating a model to a certain year's social accounting matrix (SAM) – which is usually based on a balanced national input output (IO) table – the resulting “benchmark” equilibrium depicts the status of the respective national real economy in terms of annual flows across sectors and agents of that specific year. This benchmark equilibrium can then be disturbed (or “shocked”) to learn about the potential long-term consequences of a specific exogenous economic system intervention. After introducing such a disturbance (for example a CO₂ tax), all economic sectors and agents adjust to the respective altered conditions of the system (for example the higher prices for CO₂ intensive goods) by finding new optima in their production and consumption processes. Since all sectors and agents are directly and indirectly connected via the underlying IO structure, these adjustment processes trigger second-round effects with indirect effects across the whole economic system. The described optimization processes continue until eventually a new equilibrium emerges which again fulfils the macroeconomic balances and the conditions of general equilibrium. By comparing system variables (e.g., prices, quantities or macroeconomic indicators such as real GDP) prior and after the intervention, one can learn about the economy-wide and long-term effects of the modelled system intervention.

Figure 1: Conceptual overview of the WEGDYN-AT small open economy CGE model

The WEGDYN-AT model depicts Austria’s economy as small open economy with multiple economic production sectors and final demand agents. Figure 1 gives a simplified conceptual overview of WEGDYN-AT. It shows flows of goods and services as well as production factors, while the respective monetary flows (revenues from sales, factor remunerations, transfers and taxes) run in the respective opposite directions (but are not shown). Private households (privHH) are endowed with the production factors labour (L) and capital (K) and obtain transfers from the government (GOV). The production factors are used in domestic production (X) together with intermediate inputs to produce goods and services which are either used domestically or exported (EX). Foreign trade is implemented following Armington (1969), stating that domestically produced and foreign goods are not perfectly substitutable, thus imports (IM) and goods from domestic production (D) are treated differently. The so called “Armington aggregate” (G) bundles goods coming from domestic production and other world regions, which can be substituted according to sector specific elasticities. Goods from the “mixed” Armington aggregate are then either used as intermediate inputs for production or are used in final demand for consumption by private households (privHH) and the government (GOV) as well as for investments. The government collects taxes which are levied on L and K (input taxes) as well as taxes on production and consumption (output taxes).

In general, production and consumption functions are modelled as nested Constant Elasticity of Substitution (CES) functions, with the specific cases of Cobb-Douglas and Leontief functions with respective values of

elasticities of either 1 (Cobb-Douglas) or 0 (Leontief). For the non-technical model description in this section the production and consumption functions are shown graphically as nesting trees, whereas the algebraic model formulation – which closely follows the graphical representation – is given in section 2.

The following convention is used, when showing nesting trees: whenever input combinations are illustrated as an inverted T, this means that the elasticity of substitution across inputs is zero (i.e. Leontief; constant quantity shares), whereas an inverted V stands for an elasticity larger than 0 (i.e. flexible possibility for substitution according to relative price changes). In some cases, constant elasticity of transformation (CET) functions are used, which are illustrated as a V in the nesting trees. Figure 2 shows a generic nesting tree for illustration. The chosen values for elasticities are either shown directly in the nesting tree, or – when the function is sector/household-specific – in the respective table of this documentation (see section 4.5). If not stated differently, each function generates a single output, by combining multiple inputs. A crucial feature of the WEGDYN-AT model are CO₂ emissions (differentiated between emissions regulated via the EU Emission Trading System [ETS] and non-ETS emissions), which are modelled in terms of emission certificates that need to be purchased by a sector or household whenever an input is associated with CO₂ emissions (e.g. due to the combustion of a fossil fuel). This means that emissions (certificates) are treated as inputs in the production structures and as they are physically bound to the quantity of the input that cause the emission (e.g. the fossil fuel), the input of CO₂ emission certificates is always modelled as a fixed share (i.e. Leontief with an elasticity of substitution of zero). The corresponding revenue from selling emission certificates goes to the government agent by default.

Figure 2: Generic nesting tree for a CES function at the top level (A), a further CES nest (B) and a Leontief nest (C) and at the second level.

Regarding software, the WEGDYN-AT mode is implemented in GAMS-MPS/GE, developed by Rutherford (1999) and solved using the PATH solver (Ferris and Munson, 2000). Model code and data can be provided upon request to the author of this document.

1.2. Supply side

1.2.1. Domestic production

1.2.1.1. General production

Domestic production X of sector i is modelled as a nested constant elasticity of substitution (CES) function. Figure 3 shows the respective nesting tree, which represents the production function for all sectors i as listed in Table 1, except the energy sectors (ELYS, HEATS, GASS) and the metals sector (META). Note that the shown process emissions (CO2_ETS_process) only arise in the sectors CHEM, GLAS and META, for the remaining sectors these emissions are zero.

On the first level of production X of good i , a capital-labour-land-material-transport composite (KLLNE-MT) is connected to CO₂ process emissions. Further below, the composite KLLN-E can be substituted with the M-T aggregate. KLLN-E is further composed out of KLLN and E, with KLLN being the value-added aggregate of capital (K), labour (L) and land (LN). KLLN can be substituted with an energy aggregate (E),

which again is composed out of electricity (G_{ELYS}), heat (G_{HEATS}) as well as refined petroleum products (G_{FEXT}) and gas (G_{GASS}) with associated CO_2 emissions (modelled as a Leontief nest with fixed shares). The material-transport (M-T) aggregate is composed out of material inputs ($G_{1...n}$) and a transport aggregate (T). T is composed out of a freight transport demand composite (FTR) and a transport infrastructure input (G_{ST}) at fixed shares (Leontief). Note that the type of G_{ST} depends on sector i itself, with the two land freight transport service providers Rail Freight Transport (RAILFT) and Road Freight Transport (ROADFT) demanding an associated sector-specific G_{ST} (STRAIL, STROAD respectively), whereas all remaining sectors demand a generic transport infrastructure commodity (STREST). The freight transport demand composite (FTR) is a flexible composite out of Air Transport (G_{ATRA}), Water Transport (G_{WTRA}) and a further land transport aggregate (OTRA), which in turn is flexibly composed out of Rail Freight Transport (G_{RAILFT}), Road Freight Transport (G_{ROADFT}) and a Rest of Land Transport (G_{LTREST}) input.

Figure 3: Nesting tree of domestic production X.

1.2.1.2. *Energy supply*

Figure 4 shows the supply structure of electricity. At the top level there is a fixed share Leontief nesting between the generated electricity (ELY) and the required transmission, distribution and trade services

(ELY_TDT) to be able to provide electricity to the market. ELY itself is generated out of different technologies: either via certain “pure” electricity generation technologies or electricity coming from co-generation (Cog_ELY_mix). Within the pure generation technologies, the model differentiates between base load (BL) and peak load (PL) aggregates, with BL consisting of electricity from the combustion of Coal (CO), Petrol/Oil (PE), waste (WA), biomass (BM) and hydro power (HY), whereas PL is composed out of electricity from Gas (GS), Wind power (WI) as well as Photovoltaics (PV). Figure 5 shows the Leontief production structure of the pure electricity and heat generation technologies.

Figure 4: Nesting tree of electricity supply.

Figure 5: Nesting tree of pure electricity (left) and heat (right) generation technologies.

The aggregate of electricity from co-generation (Cog_ELY_mix) is composed of electricity stemming from a set of n co-generation (Cog) technologies, as shown in Figure 6 (n consists of CO-, PE-, GS-, WA- and BM-based co-generation plants). Cog is modelled as a Leontief function in its production (combination of inputs) with associated ETS CO₂ emission and – as indicated in Figure 6 – it produces two different outputs

via a Constant Elasticity of Transformation (CET) function: electricity from co-generation (Cog_ely_n) and heat from co-generation (Cog_heat_n), subject to an elasticity of transformation of zero.

Figure 6: Production and transformation structure of co-generation technologies. Note: n consists of CO-, PE-, GS-, WA- and BM-based co-generation plants.

Heat supply, as shown in Figure 7, is implemented in a similar, but somewhat simpler, way as electricity supply. Again, there are pure technologies, generating only heat (PE = petrol/oil, GS = gas, WA = waste, BM = biomass, GE = geothermal, OT = other, SO = solar), which are subsumed in the HEAT_mix composite, which in turn is combined with heat coming from the different co-generation technologies.

Figure 7: Nesting tree of heat supply.

The supply of gas (X_{GASS}) is modelled via a Leontief production function, as shown in Figure 8. Note that the emissions in this production functions are not those that arise during the combustion of the supplied gas, but reflect the emissions that come about with the processes of refining. Whenever gas is used elsewhere in the economy the associated emissions from combustion are accounted for there (see e.g. Figure 3).

Figure 8: Nesting tree of gas supply.

1.2.1.3. Production of basic metals

Figure 9 shows the nesting tree of the supply of Basic Metals (META). The whole production process is modelled as a Leontief production function, so all inputs are combined at fixed shares. META is composed out of two different aggregates. First, IS_mix is an aggregate that accounts for crude steel production, and second a Rest of Metals Production (MTR) that accounts for the downstream processing of metals. IS_mix is composed out of a combination of conventionally produced crude steel via the blast-furnace basic-oxygen-furnace (BFB) technology (the currently dominant technology in Austria) and an alternative hydrogen-based production technology (HDE, based on Mayer et al. (2019)). Note that only the BFB technology emits CO₂ (both from combustion and from processes) whereas HDE does not. MTR itself follows the same production structure as X.

Figure 9: Nesting tree of the supply of basic metals (META).

1.2.2. Factor supply

In WEGDYN-AT three production factors are used in production: Labor (L), Capital (K) and Agricultural Land (LN). Note that LN is only used in the AGRI sector (next to L and K), all other sectors only use L and K as factor inputs. None of the factors are sector- or household specific, implying that they are perfectly mobile across sectors. By definition, in CGE models such as WEGDYN-AT factor supply is limited, which reflects the long-term assumption of general equilibrium in which all production factors are optimally used, not being idle. This implies that the supply of production factors constrains overall economic activity and that, if factor availability is not changed, an equilibrium yields the optimal allocation of existing – but limited – resources.

1.3. Demand side

1.3.1. Consumption

For measuring welfare effects, we use the Hicks'ian Equivalent Variation (EV) as an indicator, which measures the change in utility from consumption due to changing prices. More precisely, the EV quantifies how much money would need to be given to (or taken away from) a consumer in order to reach her new utility level (the one that emerges after prices have changes) at original prices. Alternatively, the EV can also be interpreted in terms of real consumption possibilities, after prices and income have changed.

The implemented consumption functions follow the same logic as the production functions (consumption composites are being “produced”, which are then demanded by final demand agents). Total societal welfare is composed out of a private consumption fraction and a government consumption fraction (depicting public services that are part of overall societal welfare and added to the utility that comes from private consumption).

Figure 10 shows the consumption function for the private household.¹ At the top level a material-energy aggregate (M-E) is traded off with a household transport aggregate (Th). The composite M-E consists of a material input aggregate Mh and an energy input aggregate E, both modelled as CES functions. Note that E also includes the consumption (combustion) of gas (G_{GASS}) and fossil fuels (G_{FEXT}), with associated CO₂ emissions. The transport aggregate is modelled as Leontief consumption pattern, consisting of air transport (G_{ATRA}), water transport (G_{WTRA}) and a land transport composite (LT). LT again is split into a fraction of public land transport (PLT) and a motorized individual transport mix (ITmix). PLT is composed out of fixed shares of short distance (SHRT) and long-distance transport services (LONG). SHRT is split into City Passenger Transport (G_{CITYPT}) and a Rest (G_{LTREST}) (covering taxis), and LONG into Rail Passenger Transport (G_{RAILPT}) and Road Passenger Transport (G_{ROADPT}). The composition of ITmix and its precursors is shown in Figure 11. ITmix is used to exogenously set the mix of combustion based motorized individual transport (MIT) and electrified motorized individual transport (EIT). The consumption function of the public households is somewhat simpler, with transport demand being not treated as a separate nest as shown in Figure 12.

¹ Note that WEGDYN-AT features twelve private households in total (see section 4 for details), but the underlying consumption function is the same for each household h . Yet, households differ in terms of their expenditure shares in consumption as well their elasticities of substitution concerning the trade-off between public land transport (PLT) and individual land transport (ITmix).

Figure 10: Nesting tree of the consumption function of private households.

Figure 11: Nesting tree of the production of fossil fuel-based motorized individual transport (MIT), electrified individual transport (EIT) and the mix between MIT and EIT.

Figure 12: Nesting tree of the consumption function of the public household.

1.3.2. Investment

The composition of investments is assumed to be fixed, as shown in Figure 13. Note that this does not mean that investment itself is assumed to be constant, but only its structural composition (e.g. shares of machinery, construction, cars etc. that characterize economy-wide investment).

Figure 13: Nesting tree of the investment bundle.

1.4. Foreign trade

As indicated in Figure 1, foreign trade is modelled via the Armington trade logic, with imports being imperfect substitutes for domestically produced goods (Armington, 1969). Further, Austria is modelled as a small open economy, meaning that Austria cannot change world market prices by changing imports or exports. The logic behind the trade modelling is shown in Figure 14. A generic foreign exchange (FX) is

created by exporting goods and services (EX), which is assumed to be fixed in its structure (Leontief). The generated FX is used to purchase imports (IM), implying that imports are bound to the availability of total FX. Imports and domestically produced goods (D) are then combined in the “Armington-aggregate” G_i , subject to sector specific elasticities. The “Armington-good” G_i is then ultimately used in the economy either in production processes as intermediate input or in final demand (consumption and investment). The decision of how much of domestic production is domestically supplied (D) or used for exports is modelled via a CET function (DS).

Figure 14: Nesting trees and logic of the Armington-foreign trade implementation.

2. Algebraic model formulation

2.1. Generic model formulation

This subsection lays out a generic model formulation and explains the notation that is used to specify the model formulation of WEGDYN-AT in the subsequent subsections. Generally, a CGE model can be formulated as a system of non-linear inequalities. More precisely the Arrow-Debreu economic equilibrium is stated as a mixed complementarity problem (MCP) where three conditions – formulated as inequalities – must be satisfied (cf. Paltsev, 2004):

- i. Zero profit
- ii. Market clearance
- iii. Income balance

Each of these conditions is explained generically in sections 2.1.1 (zero profit), 2.1.2 (market clearance) and 2.1.3 (income balance), and the specific algebraic model formulation follows the same system.

2.1.1. Zero profit

The zero profit-condition requires that profits are either zero, with activity levels y being positive, or profits are negative with activity levels being zero. This reflects the assumption of perfect competition under which entrepreneurs enter businesses as long as positive profits are possible. This happens until a point is reached where no more (extra) profits can be made. It follows the principle of “conservation of value” under which all revenue from an activity is allocated to expenditures for either intermediate inputs, factors or tax payments. Put differently this means that the value of inputs equals the value of the produced output of an activity (e.g., sector). In terms of MCP notation it can be written as follows:

$$-profit \geq 0, \quad y \geq 0, \quad output^T(-profit)$$

In the algebraic model formulation for the zero profit conditions, the unit profit function is used for notation.

An activity’s profits π is the difference between revenue R and costs C :

$$\pi = R - C$$

with R being the product of price p , activity level y (scaling factor, which is calibrated to 1 in the benchmark) and absolute benchmark output \bar{Y} . Note that whenever there is a bar above an element it denotes that it is exogenously given by the benchmark data to which the model is calibrated.

$$R = p * y * \bar{Y}$$

The formulation of the cost function depends on the production function. For the general case of a CES production function, such as

$$y_j = \bar{y}_j \left[\sum_i \theta_i \left(\frac{x_i}{\bar{x}_i} \right)^\rho \right]^{1/\rho} \text{ with } \rho := (\sigma - 1)/\sigma$$

the associated cost function of an activity j in calibrated share form is (cf. Böhringer et al., 2003):

$$C_j = \bar{C}_j \left[\sum_i \theta_i \left(\frac{w_i}{\bar{w}_i} \right)^{1-\sigma} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma)} \frac{y_j}{\bar{y}_j}$$

For a sector j , the parameter θ is the value share of each input i as given by the SAM, x are the input quantities of each input and σ is the elasticity of substitution between inputs i . In the cost function, C is absolute production costs and w the respective input price (for commodities and factors). By combining the equations for profits, revenue and costs the following inequality for the zero profit-condition is obtained:

$$p_j \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_j} \left[\sum_i \theta_j^i \left(\frac{w_i}{\bar{w}_i} \right)^{1-\sigma} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma)}$$

This equation shows that the unit price of an activity must not be lower than the required unit costs, otherwise the activity would not operate (by complementary slackness).

2.1.2. Market clearance

The market clearance condition requires that for all commodities produced and all endowed factors either supply equals demand with prices p being positive, or, if supply is larger than demand (i.e., there is excess supply), prices are zero. This condition reflects the principle of “conservation of product” in general equilibrium, in which all markets are cleared simultaneously. In terms of MCP notation it can be written as follows:

$$\text{supply} - \text{demand} \geq 0, \quad p \geq 0, \quad p^T(\text{supply} - \text{demand}) = 0$$

The general form of a CES demand function in production (capturing both intermediate and factor demand under index i) in calibrated share form can be written as follows (cf. Böhringer et al., 2003):

$$x_i = \bar{x}_i \frac{y}{\bar{y}} \left(\frac{c \bar{w}_i}{\bar{c} w_i} \right)^\sigma$$

with x_i showing the demanded quantities for intermediate or factor inputs i in production of y with associated input prices w_i and unit costs c (of production of y). The modelling of goods for final demand follows the same logic as the consumption and investment bundles are technically “produced” using CES or Leontief production functions. For demanded quantities in final demand d_i the equation looks as follows:

$$d_i = \bar{d}_i \frac{IN}{\bar{IN}} \left(\frac{e \bar{w}_i}{\bar{e} w_i} \right)^\sigma$$

With d_i showing the demanded quantities of commodities i in final demand, with IN being income (the sum of all factor incomes) and e unit costs of final demand (for consumption or investment bundles). Following the notation in terms of a MCP, the market clearance-condition that sets supply equal to demand can be shown as an inequality:

$$\bar{Y}_i y_i \geq \sum_j x_{ij} + \sum_z d_{iz}$$

So, the supply of i is larger or equal to the sum of intermediate demand (sum over all sectors j that use i in their production) and final demand (sum over all final demand activities z). The inequality of market clearance for (limited) factors F is (with f denoting all factors in the economy):

$$\bar{F}_f \geq \sum_j x_{fj}$$

2.1.3. Income balance

The income balance-condition is straightforward and requires that the value of total income equals the value of endowments (factor remuneration) and/or tax income and/or transfers. This condition can be formulated as follows:

$$income = endowment + taxrev + transfers$$

2.2. Zero profit conditions

2.2.1. Production of general commodities

Following the notation as introduced in 2.1, the following subsections provide the zero-profit conditions for each activity's output and respective input composites as presented graphically in section 0. Note that production functions are not shown explicitly, as they are implicitly captured via the notation based on cost functions. Further note, that exogenous tax rates nor CO₂ emissions are shown in the algebraic model formulation for the sake of readability. Tax rates would need to be included by multiplying input prices w times $(1 - taxrate)$. The modelling of CO₂ emission is explained in section 1.1 (Leontief fixed shares).

2.2.1.1. Production of goods and services (X)

The price of the production X of commodity i is determined by the KLLNE-MT composite and in some special cases also process emissions which would be added at the top level of the nesting tree. Note that top level CO₂ process emissions are omitted from the equation (please see respective nesting trees for details):

$$p_i^X \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^X} \left(\frac{w_i^{KLLNE-MT}}{\bar{w}_i^{KLLNE-MT}} \right)$$

2.2.1.2. Capital-labour-land-energy-material-transport composite (KLLNE-MT)

$$p_i^{KLLNE-MT} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^{KLLNE-MT}} \left[\theta_i^{KLLNE} \left(\frac{w_i^{KLLNE}}{\bar{w}_i^{KLLNE}} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{top}} + \theta_i^{MT} \left(\frac{w_i^{MT}}{\bar{w}_i^{MT}} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{top}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma_i^{top})}$$

2.2.1.3. Capital-labour-land-energy composite (KLLN-E)

$$p_i^{KLLN-E} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^{KLLN-E}} \left[\theta_i^{KLLN} \left(\frac{w_i^{KLLN}}{\bar{w}_i^{KLLN}} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{kle}} + \theta_i^E \left(\frac{w_i^E}{\bar{w}_i^E} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{kle}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma_i^{kle})}$$

2.2.1.4. Material-transport composite (M-T)

$$p_i^{M-T} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^{M-T}} \left[\theta_i^M \left(\frac{w_i^M}{\bar{w}_i^M} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{mfi}} + \theta_i^T \left(\frac{w_i^T}{\bar{w}_i^T} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{mfi}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma_i^{mfi})}$$

2.2.1.5. Capital-labour-land composite (KLLN)

$$p_i^{KLLN} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^{KLLN}} \left[\theta_i^K \left(\frac{w^K}{\bar{w}^K} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{kl}} + \theta_i^L \left(\frac{w^L}{\bar{w}^L} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{kl}} + \theta_i^K \left(\frac{w^{LN}}{\bar{w}^{LN}} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{kl}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma_i^{kl})}$$

2.2.1.6. Energy composite (E)

The energy composite combines energy inputs. Note that *nrg* includes only the energy sectors ELYS, HEATS, FEXT and GASS. Also note that CO₂ emissions are associated to the combustion of FEXT and GASS and are also explicitly modelled, however not shown in the equation.

$$p_i^E \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^E} \left[\sum_{nrg} \theta_i^{G,nrg} \left(\frac{w^{G,nrg}}{\bar{w}^{G,nrg}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{ene}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^{ene})}$$

2.2.1.7. Material composite (M)

Note that *j* in the equation for *M* includes all sectors, except the energy sectors, freight transport service sectors as well as transport infrastructure providers.

$$p_i^M \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^M} \left[\sum_j \theta_i^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{int}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma_i^{int})}$$

2.2.1.8. Transport composite (T)

Note that the type of transport infrastructure input (G_{ST}) depends on sector *i* itself, with the two land freight transport service providers Rail Freight Transport (RAILFT) and Road Freight Transport (ROADFT) demanding an associated sector-specific G_{ST} (STRAIL, STROAD respectively), whereas all remaining sectors demand a generic transport infrastructure commodity (STREST).

$$p_i^T \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^T} \left[\theta_i^{G,ST^*} \left(\frac{w^{G,ST^*}}{\bar{w}^{G,ST^*}} \right) + \theta_i^E \left(\frac{w_i^{FTR}}{\bar{w}_i^{FTR}} \right) \right]$$

2.2.1.9. Freight transport composite (FTR)

$$p_i^{FTR} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^{FTR}} \left[\theta_i^{ATRA} \left(\frac{W_{G,ATRA}}{\bar{W}_{G,ATRA}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{flaw}} + \theta_i^{WTRA} \left(\frac{W_{G,WTRA}}{\bar{W}_{G,WTRA}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{flaw}} + \theta_i^{OTRA} \left(\frac{W_i^{OTRA}}{\bar{W}_i^{OTRA}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{flaw}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^{flaw})}$$

2.2.1.10. Land freight transport composite (OTRA)

$$p_i^{OTRA} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^{OTRA}} \left[\sum_{trans} \theta_i^{G,trans} \left(\frac{W_{G,trans}}{\bar{W}_{G,trans}} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{frrr}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma_i^{frrr})}$$

Note that *trans* includes only the land freight transport service providing sectors RAILFT, ROADFT and LTREST.

2.2.2. Production of energy commodities

2.2.2.1. Electricity supply (ELYS)

$$p_{ELYS}^X \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_{ELYS}^X} \left[\theta^{ELY} \left(\frac{W^{ELY}}{\bar{W}^{ELY}} \right) + \theta^{ELY_TDT} \left(\frac{W^{ELY_TDT}}{\bar{W}^{ELY_TDT}} \right) \right]$$

2.2.2.2. Electricity generation composite (ELY)

$$p^{ELY} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{ELY}} \left(\theta^{ELY_mix} \left(\frac{W^{ELY_mix}}{\bar{W}^{ELY_mix}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{esmix}} + \theta^{Cog_ELY_mix} \left(\frac{W^{Cog_ELY_mix}}{\bar{W}^{Cog_ELY_mix}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{esmix}} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\sigma^{esmix}}}$$

2.2.2.3. Transmission, distribution and trade of electricity (ELY_TDT)

ELY_TDT is specified as a Leontief nesting and with a combination in fixed shares of intermediate inputs G from all other sector j and factors f (capital and labour).

$$p^{ELY_TDT} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{ELY_TDT}} \left[\sum_j \theta^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right) + \sum_f \theta^f \left(\frac{w^f}{\bar{w}^f} \right) \right]$$

2.2.2.4. Baseload-Peakload electricity composite (ELY_mix)

$$p^{ELY_mix} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{ELY_mix}} \left[\theta^{BL} \left(\frac{w^{BL}}{\bar{w}^{BL}} \right) + \theta^{PL} \left(\frac{w^{PL}}{\bar{w}^{PL}} \right) \right]$$

2.2.2.5. Cogenerated electricity composite (Cog_ELY_mix)

Cog_ELY_mix is modelled a CES function that combines electricity from the different cogeneration technologies *celyt* (CO-, PE-, GS-, WA- and BM-based co-generation plants).

$$p^{Cog_ELY_mix} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{Cog_ELY_mix}} \left[\sum_{celyt} \theta^{celyt} \left(\frac{w^{celyt}}{\bar{w}^{celyt}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{cemix}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^{cemix})}$$

2.2.2.6. Baseload composite in electricity production (BL)

The Baseload-electricity composite is composed of outputs from *elytec* which include the electricity generation technologies CO_ely, PE_ely, WA_ely, BM_ely, HY_ely.

$$p^{BL} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{BL}} \left[\sum_{elytec} \theta^{elytec} \left(\frac{w^{elytec}}{\bar{w}^{elytec}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{blmix}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^{blmix})}$$

2.2.2.7. Peakload composite in electricity production (PL)

$$p^{PL} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{PL}} \left(\theta^{GS_ely} \left(\frac{W^{GS_ely}}{\bar{W}^{GS_ely}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{plmix}} + \theta^{WI_ely} \left(\frac{W^{WI_ely}}{\bar{W}^{WI_ely}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{plmix}} + \theta^{PV_ely} \left(\frac{W^{PV_ely}}{\bar{W}^{PV_ely}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{plmix}} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\sigma^{plmix}}}$$

2.2.2.8. Individual electricity generation technologies (*_ely)

Individual electricity generation technologies are modelled as Leontief production. Note that when fossil fuels are used, CO₂ emissions are emerging.

$$p^{elytec} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{elytec}} \left[\sum_j \theta^{G,j} \left(\frac{W^{G,j}}{\bar{W}^{G,j}} \right) + \sum_f \theta^f \left(\frac{W^f}{\bar{W}^f} \right) \right]$$

2.2.2.9. Heat supply (HEATS)

$$p_{HEATS}^X \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_{HEATS}^X} \left(\theta^{HEAT_mix} \left(\frac{W^{HEAT_mix}}{\bar{W}^{HEAT_mix}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{hsmix}} + \theta^{Cog_HEAT_mix} \left(\frac{W^{Cog_HEAT_mix}}{\bar{W}^{Cog_HEAT_mix}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{hsmix}} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\sigma^{hsmix}}}$$

2.2.2.10. Heat generation composite (HEAT_mix)

The heat generation composite is composed of outputs from *heatec* which include the heat generation technologies PE_hea, GS_hea, WA_hea, BM_hea, GE_hea, OT_hea, SO_hea.

$$p^{HEAT_mix} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{HEAT_mix}} \left[\sum_{heatec} \theta^{heatec} \left(\frac{w^{heatec}}{\bar{w}^{heatec}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{hmix}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^{hmix})}$$

2.2.2.11. Cogenerated heat composite (Cog_HEAT_mix)

Cog_HEAT_mix is modelled a CES function that combines heat from the different cogeneration technologies *cheat* (CO-, PE-, GS-, WA- and BM-based co-generation plants).

$$p^{Cog_HEAT_mix} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{Cog_HEAT_mix}} \left[\sum_{cheat} \theta^{cheat} \left(\frac{w^{cheat}}{\bar{w}^{cheat}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{chmix}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^{chmix})}$$

2.2.2.12. Individual heat generation technologies (*_hea)

Individual heat generation technologies are modelled as Leontief production. Note that when fossil fuels are used, CO₂ emissions are emerging.

$$p^{heatec} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{heatec}} \left[\sum_j \theta^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right) + \sum_f \theta^f \left(\frac{w^f}{\bar{w}^f} \right) \right]$$

2.2.2.13. Co-generation of heat and electricity (Cog)

Co-generation plants generate in fixed shares according to a constant elasticity of transformation (CET) function both electricity (Cog_ely) and heat (Cog_heat). Note that the elasticity of transformation is zero.

There are n different co-generation plants (CO-, PE-, GS-, WA- and BM-based co-generation plants), so $n = celyt = cheat$.

$$p_n^{Cog} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_n^{Cog}} \left[\theta_n^{Cog_ely} \left(\frac{w_n^{Cog_ely}}{\bar{w}_n^{Cog_ely}} \right) + \theta_n^{Cog_heat} \left(\frac{w_n^{Cog_heat}}{\bar{w}_n^{Cog_heat}} \right) \right]$$

At the same time, each co-generation plant produces according to a Leontief production function with inputs (Armington goods) from all other sectors j and production factors f :

$$p_n^{Cog} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_n^{Cog}} \left[\sum_j \theta^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right) + \sum_f \theta^f \left(\frac{w^f}{\bar{w}^f} \right) \right]$$

2.2.2.14. Gas supply (GASS)

Gas supply is modelled as a Leontief production function, combining intermediate inputs G from all sectors j and factors f .

$$p_{GASS}^X \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_{GASS}^X} \left[\sum_j \theta^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right) + \sum_f \theta^f \left(\frac{w^f}{\bar{w}^f} \right) \right]$$

2.2.3. Production of basic metals

The production of META is straightforward, as all composites are nested with elasticities of substitution of zero. This means that the whole production process in a single Leontief production function. Note that MTR has the same production structure than X (see section 1.2.1.1). Also note that BFB also includes process based and combustion based ETS and non-ETS emissions.

$$p^{BFB} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{BFB}} \left[\sum_j \theta^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right) + \sum_f \theta^f \left(\frac{w^f}{\bar{w}^f} \right) \right]$$

$$p^{HDE} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{HDE}} \left[\sum_j \theta^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right) + \sum_f \theta^f \left(\frac{w^f}{\bar{w}^f} \right) \right]$$

$$p^{IS_MIX} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{IS_MIX}} \left[\theta^{BFB} \left(\frac{w^{BFB}}{\bar{w}^{BFB}} \right) + \theta^{HDE} \left(\frac{w^{HDE}}{\bar{w}^{HDE}} \right) \right]$$

2.2.4. Consumption functions

Private consumption is household (h) specific and is modelled as a nested CES consumption function. For the sake of readability, the h index is not shown in the equations of private consumption.

2.2.4.1. Private consumption (W)

$$p^W \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^W} \left[\theta^{ME} \left(\frac{w^{ME}}{\bar{w}^{ME}} \right)^{1-\sigma^s} + \theta^{Th} \left(\frac{w^{Th}}{\bar{w}^{Th}} \right)^{1-\sigma^s} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^s)}$$

2.2.4.2. Material-energy composite in private consumption (M-E)

$$p^{ME} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{ME}} \left[\theta^M \left(\frac{w_h^{Mh}}{\bar{w}_h^{Mh}} \right)^{1-\sigma^v} + \theta^E \left(\frac{w^E}{\bar{w}^E} \right)^{1-\sigma^v} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^v)}$$

2.2.4.3. Material composite in private consumption (Mh)

$$p_i^{Mh} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^{Mh}} \left[\sum_j \theta_i^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{nene}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma_i^{nene})}$$

2.2.4.4. Energy composite (E)

This is the same function as used in production of commodities.

$$p_i^E \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^E} \left[\sum_{nrg} \theta_i^{G,nrg} \left(\frac{w^{G,nrg}}{\bar{w}^{G,nrg}} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{ene}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma_i^{ene})}$$

2.2.4.5. Transport composite in private consumption (Th)

The transport composite of households is modelled as a Leontief function with fixed shares.

$$p^{Th} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{Th}} \left[\theta^{G,ATRA} \left(\frac{w^{G,ATRA}}{\bar{w}^{G,ATRA}} \right) + \theta^{WTRA} \left(\frac{w^{G,WTRA}}{\bar{w}^{G,WTRA}} \right) + \theta^{LT} \left(\frac{w^{LT}}{\bar{w}^{LT}} \right) \right]$$

2.2.4.6. Land-transport composite in private consumption (LT)

$$p^{LT} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{LT}} \left[\theta^{PLT} \left(\frac{w^{PLT}}{\bar{w}^{PLT}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{mipu}} + \theta^{ITmix} \left(\frac{w^{ITmix}}{\bar{w}^{ITmix}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{mipu}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^{mipu})}$$

2.2.4.7. Passenger land transport composite in private consumption (PLT)

$$p^{PLT} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{PLT}} \left[\theta^{SHRT} \left(\frac{w^{SHRT}}{\bar{w}^{SHRT}} \right) + \theta^{LONG} \left(\frac{w^{LONG}}{\bar{w}^{LONG}} \right) \right]$$

2.2.4.8. Short-range land transport (SHRT)

$$p^{SHRT} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{SHRT}} \left[\theta^{G,CITYPT} \left(\frac{w^{G,CITYPT}}{\bar{w}^{G,CITYPT}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{city}} + \theta^{G,LTREST} \left(\frac{w^{G,LTREST}}{\bar{w}^{G,LTREST}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{city}} \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\sigma^{city}}}$$

2.2.4.9. Long-range land transport (LONG)

$$p^{LONG} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{LONG}} \left[\theta^{G,RAILPT} \left(\frac{w^{G,RAILPT}}{\bar{w}^{G,RAILPT}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{rota}} + \theta^{G,ROADPT} \left(\frac{w^{G,ROADPT}}{\bar{w}^{G,ROADPT}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{rota}} \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\sigma^{rota}}}$$

2.2.4.10. Motorized individual transport (MIT)

MIT is modelled as a Leontief function, which does not need production factors. Note that due to the combustion of fossil fuels also CO₂ emissions are emerging in MIT.

$$p^{MIT} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{MIT}} \left[\sum_j \theta^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right) \right]$$

2.2.4.11. Electrified individual transport (EIT)

EIT has a similar production structure than MIT, but there are no direct emissions involved.

$$p^{EIT} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{EIT}} \left[\sum_j \theta^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right) \right]$$

2.2.4.12. Individual transport mix (ITmix)

$$p^{ITmix} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{ITmix}} \left[\theta^{MIT} \left(\frac{w^{MIT}}{\bar{w}^{MIT}} \right) + \theta^{EIT} \left(\frac{w^{EIT}}{\bar{w}^{EIT}} \right) \right]$$

2.2.4.13. Public consumption (WGOV)

$$p^{WGOV} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{WGOV}} \left[\theta^{Mg} \left(\frac{w^{Mg}}{\bar{w}^{Mg}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{sg}} + \theta^{Eg} \left(\frac{w^{Eg}}{\bar{w}^{Eg}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{sg}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^{sg})}$$

2.2.4.14. Material composite in government consumption (Mg)

$$p^{Mg} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{Mg}} \left[\sum_j \theta^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{nene}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^{nene})}$$

2.2.4.15. Energy composite in government consumption (Eg)

$$p^{Eg} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{Eg}} \left[\sum_j \theta^{G,j} \left(\frac{w^{G,j}}{\bar{w}^{G,j}} \right)^{1-\sigma^{ene}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma^{ene})}$$

2.2.5. Investment

The investment activity is modelled as a Leontief production function, that combines different goods at constant shares.

$$p_{INV}^X \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_{INV}^X} \left[\sum_i \theta^{G,i} \left(\frac{w^{G,i}}{\bar{w}^{G,i}} \right) \right]$$

2.2.6. Foreign trade and domestic supply

2.2.6.1. Foreign exchange and exports (FX)

$$p^{FX} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{FX}} \left[\sum_i \theta^{EX,i} \left(\frac{w^{EX,i}}{\bar{w}^{EX,i}} \right) \right]$$

2.2.6.2. Imports (IM)

Due to the small open economy assumption, import prices only change due to changes in the exchange rate (i.e. the relative price of FX).

$$p_i^{IM} \leq p^{FX}$$

2.2.6.3. Armington good (G)

For each commodity i an Armington good G is generated out of domestically produced goods (D) and imports (IM) of the same type of commodity.

$$p_i^G \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^G} \left[\theta^{D,i} \left(\frac{w^{D,i}}{\bar{w}^{D,i}} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{armi}} + \theta^{IM,i} \left(\frac{w^{IM,i}}{\bar{w}^{IM,i}} \right)^{1-\sigma_i^{armi}} \right]^{1/(1-\sigma_i^{armi})}$$

2.2.6.4. Domestic supply (DS)

Domestic supply (DS) is modelled as a CET function, which decides which part of domestic production (X) stays within the country (D) and which part is being exported (EX).

$$p_i^{DS} \leq \frac{1}{\bar{y}_i^{DS}} \left[\theta^{D,i} \left(\frac{w^{D,i}}{\bar{w}^{D,i}} \right)^{1+\sigma_i^{armi}} + \theta^{EX,i} \left(\frac{w^{EX,i}}{\bar{w}^{EX,i}} \right)^{1+\sigma_i^{armi}} \right]^{1/(1+\sigma_i^{armi})}$$

$$p_i^{DS} \leq p_i^X$$

2.3. Market clearance conditions

For the algebraic model formulation of market clearance, we limit the documentation of equations to the demand equations, since supply is simply the product of activity levels and benchmark output, or – in case of factors – the benchmark endowment. For formulating demand, we follow the notation as introduced in section 2.1. Note that tax rates are not included for the sake of readability.

2.3.1. Demand equations for composites in general production X

$$x_i^{KLLNE-MT} = \bar{x}_i^{KLLNE-MT} \frac{X_i}{\bar{X}_i}$$

$$x_i^{KLLN-E} = \bar{x}_i^{KLLN-E} \frac{KLLNE-MT_i}{KLLNE-MT_i} \left(\frac{p_i^{KLLNE-MT} \bar{p}_i^{KLLN-E}}{\bar{p}_i^{KLLNE-MT} p_i^{KLLN-E}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{top}}$$

$$x_i^{M-T} = \bar{x}_i^{M-T} \frac{KLLNE-MT_i}{KLLNE-MT_i} \left(\frac{p_i^{KLLNE-MT} \bar{p}_i^{M-T}}{\bar{p}_i^{KLLNE-MT} p_i^{M-T}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{top}}$$

$$x_i^{KLLN} = \bar{x}_i^{KLLN} \frac{KLLN-E_i}{KLLN-E_i} \left(\frac{p_i^{KLLN-E} \bar{p}_i^{KLLN}}{\bar{p}_i^{KLLN-E} p_i^{KLLN}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{kle}}$$

$$x_i^E = \bar{x}_i^E \frac{KLLN-E_i}{KLLN-E_i} \left(\frac{p_i^{KLLN-E} \bar{p}_i^E}{\bar{p}_i^{KLLN-E} p_i^E} \right)^{\sigma_i^{kle}}$$

$$x_i^M = \bar{x}_i^M \frac{M-T_i}{M-T_i} \left(\frac{p_i^{M-T} \bar{p}_i^M}{\bar{p}_i^{M-T} p_i^M} \right)^{\sigma_i^{mfi}}$$

$$x_i^T = \bar{x}_i^T \frac{M-T_i}{M-T_i} \left(\frac{p_i^{M-T} \bar{p}_i^T}{\bar{p}_i^{M-T} p_i^T} \right)^{\sigma_i^{mfi}}$$

$$x_i^{FTR} = \bar{x}_i^T \frac{T_i}{\bar{T}_i}$$

$$x_i^{OTRA} = \bar{x}_i^{OTRA} \frac{FTR_i}{FTR_i} \left(\frac{p_i^{FTR} \bar{p}_i^{OTRA}}{\bar{p}_i^{FTR} p_i^{OTRA}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{flaw}}$$

2.3.1. Demand equations for composites in the production of energy commodities

$$x^{ELY} = \bar{x}^{ELY} \frac{X^{ELYS}}{\bar{X}^{ELYS}}$$

$$x^{ELY_TDT} = \bar{x}^{ELY_TDT} \frac{X^{ELYS}}{\bar{X}^{ELYS}}$$

$$x^{ELY_mix} = \bar{x}^{ELY_mix} \frac{ELY}{\bar{ELY}} \left(\frac{p^{ELY} \bar{p}^{ELY_mix}}{\bar{p}^{ELY} p^{ELY_mix}} \right)^{\sigma^{esmix}}$$

$$x^{Cog_ELY_mix} = \bar{x}^{Cog_ELY_mix} \frac{ELY}{\bar{ELY}} \left(\frac{p^{ELY} \bar{p}^{Cog_ELY_mix}}{\bar{p}^{ELY} p^{Cog_ELY_mix}} \right)^{\sigma^{esmix}}$$

$$x^{BL} = \bar{x}^{BL} \frac{ELY_mix}{\bar{ELY_mix}}$$

$$x^{PL} = \bar{x}^{PL} \frac{ELY_mix}{\bar{ELY_mix}}$$

$$x^{elytec} = \bar{x}^{elytec} \frac{BL}{\bar{BL}} \left(\frac{p^{BL} \bar{p}^{elytec}}{\bar{p}^{BL} p^{elytec}} \right)^{\sigma^{blmix}} \quad \text{with } elytec = \{CO, PE, WA, BM, HY\}$$

$$x^{elytec} = \bar{x}^{elytec} \frac{PL}{\bar{PL}} \left(\frac{p^{PL} \bar{p}^{elytec}}{\bar{p}^{PL} p^{elytec}} \right)^{\sigma^{plmix}} \quad \text{with } elytec = \{GS, WI, PV\}$$

$$x^{HEAT_mix} = \bar{x}^{HEAT_mix} \frac{X^{HEATS}}{\bar{X}^{HEATS}} \left(\frac{p^{X,HEATS} \bar{p}^{HEAT_mix}}{\bar{p}^{X,HEATS} p^{HEAT_mix}} \right)^{\sigma^{hsmix}}$$

$$x^{Cog_HEAT_mix} = \bar{x}^{Cog_HEAT_mix} \frac{X^{HEATS}}{\bar{X}^{HEATS}} \left(\frac{p^{X,HEATS} \bar{p}^{Cog_HEAT_mix}}{\bar{p}^{X,HEATS} p^{Cog_HEAT_mix}} \right)^{\sigma^{hsmix}}$$

$$x^{heatec} = \bar{x}^{heatec} \frac{HEAT_mix}{\bar{HEAT_mix}} \left(\frac{p^{HEAT_mix} \bar{p}^{heatec}}{\bar{p}^{HEAT_mix} p^{heatec}} \right)^{\sigma^{hmix}}$$

$$x_{celyt}^{Cog_ely} = \bar{x}_{celyt}^{Cog_ely} \frac{Cog_ELY_mix}{\overline{Cog_ELY_mix}} \left(\frac{p^{Cog_ELY_mix} \bar{p}_{celyt}^{Cog_ely}}{\bar{p}^{Cog_ELY_mix} p_{celyt}^{Cog_ely}} \right)^{\sigma^{cemix}}$$

$$x_{cheat}^{Cog_heat} = \bar{x}_{cheat}^{Cog_heat} \frac{Cog_HEAT_mix}{\overline{Cog_HEAT_mix}} \left(\frac{p^{Cog_HEAT_mix} \bar{p}_{cheat}^{Cog_heat}}{\bar{p}^{Cog_HEAT_mix} p_{cheat}^{Cog_heat}} \right)^{\sigma^{chmix}}$$

2.3.2. Demand equations for composites in the production of basic metals

$$x^{BFB} = \bar{x}^{BFB} \frac{IS_mix}{\overline{IS_mix}}$$

$$x^{HDE} = \bar{x}^{HDE} \frac{IS_mix}{\overline{IS_mix}}$$

$$x^{MTR} = \bar{x}^{MTR} \frac{META}{\overline{META}}$$

$$x^{IS_mix} = \bar{x}^{IS_mix} \frac{META}{\overline{META}}$$

2.3.1. Demand equations for composites in consumption (W and WGOV)

$$x^{M-E} = \bar{x}^{M-E} \frac{W}{\overline{W}} \left(\frac{p^W \bar{p}^{M-E}}{\bar{p}^W p^{M-E}} \right)^{\sigma^s}$$

$$x^{Mh} = \bar{x}^{Mh} \frac{M-E}{\overline{M-E}} \left(\frac{p^{M-E} \bar{p}^{Mh}}{\bar{p}^{M-E} p^{Mh}} \right)^{\sigma^v}$$

$$x^{Eh} = \bar{x}^{Eh} \frac{M-E}{\overline{M-E}} \left(\frac{p^{M-E} \bar{p}^{Eh}}{\bar{p}^{M-E} p^{Eh}} \right)^{\sigma^v}$$

$$x^{Th} = \bar{x}^{Th} \frac{W}{\overline{W}} \left(\frac{p^W \bar{p}^{Th}}{\bar{p}^W p^{Th}} \right)^{\sigma^s}$$

$$x^{LT} = \bar{x}^{LT} \frac{Th}{\overline{Th}}$$

$$x^{PLT} = \bar{x}^{PLT} \frac{LT}{\overline{LT}} \left(\frac{p^{LT} \bar{p}^{PLT}}{\bar{p}^{LT} p^{PLT}} \right)^{\sigma^{mipu}}$$

$$x^{SHRT} = \bar{x}^{SHRT} \frac{PLT}{\overline{PLT}}$$

$$x^{LONG} = \bar{x}^{LONG} \frac{PLT}{\overline{PLT}}$$

$$x^{MIT} = \bar{x}^{MIT} \frac{ITmix}{\overline{ITmix}}$$

$$x^{EIT} = \bar{x}^{EIT} \frac{ITmix}{\overline{ITmix}}$$

$$x^{Mg} = \bar{x}^{Mg} \frac{WGOV}{\overline{WGOV}} \left(\frac{p^{WGOV} \bar{p}^{Mg}}{\bar{p}^{WGOV} p^{Mg}} \right)^{\sigma^{sg}}$$

$$x^{Eg} = \bar{x}^{Eg} \frac{WGOV}{\overline{WGOV}} \left(\frac{p^{WGOV} \bar{p}^{Eg}}{\bar{p}^{WGOV} p^{Eg}} \right)^{\sigma^{sg}}$$

2.3.2. Demand equations for domestic supply and foreign trade

To import commodities, foreign exchange is created via exporting commodities. Foreign exchange can only be used to purchase imports; thus, the value of imports equals the value of exports (fixed trade balance) and the relative price of imports equals the relative price of the foreign exchange.

2.3.2.1. Foreign exchange and exports (FX)

$$x_i^{EX} = \bar{x}_i^{EX} \frac{FX}{\overline{FX}}$$

2.3.2.2. Imports (IM)

$$x^{FX} = \bar{x}^{FX} \left(\frac{\sum_i IM_i}{\sum_i \bar{IM}_i} \right)$$

2.3.2.3. Demand for domestic (D) and import (IM) goods in the Armington aggregate

$$x_i^D = \bar{x}_i^D \frac{G_i}{\bar{G}_i} \left(\frac{p^{G,i} \bar{p}^{-D,i}}{\bar{p}^{-G,i} p^{D,i}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{armi}}$$

$$x_i^{IM} = \bar{x}_i^{IM} \frac{G_i}{\bar{G}_i} \left(\frac{p^{G,i} \bar{p}^{-IM,i}}{\bar{p}^{-G,i} p^{IM,i}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{armi}}$$

2.3.2.4. Domestic supply (DS) and exports (EX)

Supply to the domestic (D) or export market (EX) is modelled via a CET function. Output X is used in the activity DS from which it is split up into D and EX.

$$x_i^D = \bar{x}_i^D \frac{DS_i}{\bar{DS}_i} \left(\frac{p^{DS,i} \bar{p}^{-D,i}}{\bar{p}^{-DS,i} p^{D,i}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{armi}}$$

$$x_i^{EX} = \bar{x}_i^{EX} \frac{DS_i}{\bar{DS}_i} \left(\frac{p^{DS,i} \bar{p}^{-EX,i}}{\bar{p}^{-DS,i} p^{EX,i}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{armi}}$$

$$x_i^X = \bar{x}_i^X \frac{DS_i}{\bar{DS}_i}$$

2.3.3. Demand equations for Armington goods (G)

2.3.3.1. Demand for general commodities

The Armington good (G) plays a central role in the model, since it is the commodity that is ultimately demanded in production (as intermediate input), consumption and the investment activity. The demand for the Armington good of commodity i (x_i^G) is thus the sum of intermediate demand (M) in generic production X of all sectors j , in the production of electricity and heat (ELY_TDT and all the electricity and heat generation technologies, including the ones of co-generation [note, there are n different co-generation

plants: CO-, PE-, GS-, WA- and BM-based co-generation plants]), gas supply (GASS), the production of basic metals (BFB and HDE) as well as private and public consumption (Mh, MIT, EIT and Mg) and investment:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_i^G = & \sum_j \bar{x}_j^{G,i} \frac{M_j}{\bar{M}_j} \left(\frac{p_j^M \bar{p}^{G,i}}{\bar{p}_j^M p^{G,i}} \right)^{\sigma^{int}} + \bar{x}_{ELY_TDT}^{G,i} \frac{ELY_TDT}{\bar{ELY_TDT}} + \sum_{elytec} \bar{x}_{elytec}^{G,i} \frac{x_{elytec}}{\bar{x}_{elytec}} + \sum_{heatec} \bar{x}_{heatec}^{G,i} \frac{x_{heatec}}{\bar{x}_{heatec}} \\
& + \sum_n \bar{x}_n^{G,i} \frac{x_n^{Cog}}{\bar{x}_n^{Cog}} + \bar{x}_{GASS}^{G,i} \frac{x^{GASS}}{\bar{x}^{GASS}} + \bar{x}_{BFB}^{G,i} \frac{x^{BFB}}{\bar{x}^{BFB}} + \bar{x}_{HDE}^{G,i} \frac{x^{HDE}}{\bar{x}^{HDE}} + \bar{x}_{Mh}^{G,i} \frac{Mh}{\bar{Mh}} \left(\frac{p^{Mh} \bar{p}^{G,i}}{\bar{p}^{Mh} p^{G,i}} \right)^{\sigma^{nene}} \\
& + \bar{x}_{MIT}^{G,i} \frac{MIT}{\bar{MIT}} + \bar{x}_{EIT}^{G,i} \frac{EIT}{\bar{EIT}} + \bar{x}_{Mg}^{G,i} \frac{Mg}{\bar{Mg}} \left(\frac{p^{Mg} \bar{p}^{G,i}}{\bar{p}^{Mg} p^{G,i}} \right)^{\sigma^{nene}} + \bar{x}_{INV}^{G,i} \frac{x^{INV}}{\bar{x}^{INV}}
\end{aligned}$$

2.3.3.2. Demand for energy commodities

The energy commodities FEXT and GASS are not demanded in the same way as the general commodities as given in 2.3.3.1, but at different points in the nested CES functions of sectors i . For FEXT demand consists of the sum of intermediate demand (E), demand for the production of electricity and heat (incl. co-generation), gas supply (GASS), the production of basic metals, energy demand of private and public households (Eh and Mg, including individual transport MIT) as well as inputs onto the investment activity:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_{FEXT}^G = & \sum_i \bar{x}_i^{G,FEXT} \frac{E_i}{\bar{E}_i} \left(\frac{p_i^E \bar{p}^{G,FEXT}}{\bar{p}_i^E p^{G,FEXT}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{ene}} + \sum_{elytec} \bar{x}_{elytec}^{G,FEXT} \frac{x_{elytec}}{\bar{x}_{elytec}} + \sum_{heatec} \bar{x}_{heatec}^{G,FEXT} \frac{x_{heatec}}{\bar{x}_{heatec}} \\
& + \sum_n \bar{x}_n^{G,FEXT} \frac{x_n^{Cog}}{\bar{x}_n^{Cog}} + \bar{x}_{GASS}^{G,FEXT} \frac{x^{GASS}}{\bar{x}^{GASS}} + \bar{x}_{BFB}^{G,FEXT} \frac{x^{BFB}}{\bar{x}^{BFB}} + \bar{x}_{Eh}^{G,FEXT} \frac{Eh}{\bar{Eh}} \left(\frac{p^{Eh} \bar{p}^{G,FEXT}}{\bar{p}^{Eh} p^{G,FEXT}} \right)^{\sigma^{ene}} \\
& + \bar{x}_{MIT}^{G,FEXT} \frac{MIT}{\bar{MIT}} + \bar{x}_{Mg}^{G,FEXT} \frac{Mg}{\bar{Mg}} \left(\frac{p^{Mg} \bar{p}^{G,FEXT}}{\bar{p}^{Mg} p^{G,FEXT}} \right)^{\sigma^{nene}} + \bar{x}_{INV}^{G,FEXT} \frac{x^{INV}}{\bar{x}^{INV}}
\end{aligned}$$

The demand equation for GASS is similar:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_{GASS}^G = & \sum_i \bar{x}_i^{G,GASS} \frac{E_i}{\bar{E}_i} \left(\frac{p_i^E \bar{p}^{G,GASS}}{\bar{p}_i^E p^{G,GASS}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{ene}} + \sum_{elytec} \bar{x}_{elytec}^{G,GASS} \frac{x_{elytec}}{\bar{x}_{elytec}} + \sum_{heatec} \bar{x}_{heatec}^{G,GASS} \frac{x_{heatec}}{\bar{x}_{heatec}} \\
& + \sum_n \bar{x}_n^{G,GASS} \frac{x_n^{Cog}}{\bar{x}_n^{Cog}} + \bar{x}_{GASS}^{G,GASS} \frac{x^{GASS}}{\bar{x}^{GASS}} + \bar{x}_{BFB}^{G,GASS} \frac{x^{BFB}}{\bar{x}^{BFB}} + \bar{x}_{Eh}^{G,GASS} \frac{Eh}{\bar{Eh}} \left(\frac{p^{Eh} \bar{p}^{G,GASS}}{\bar{p}^{Eh} p^{G,GASS}} \right)^{\sigma^{ene}} \\
& + \bar{x}_{Eg}^{G,GASS} \frac{Eg}{\bar{Eg}} \left(\frac{p^{Eg} \bar{p}^{G,GASS}}{\bar{p}^{Eg} p^{G,GASS}} \right)^{\sigma^{ene}} + \bar{x}_{INV}^{G,GASS} \frac{x^{INV}}{\bar{x}^{INV}}
\end{aligned}$$

2.3.3.3. Demand for transport services

The demand equation for air transport (ATRA) and water transport services (WTRA) is the same. For simplicity only the equation for ATRA is shown:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_{ATRA}^G = & \sum_i \bar{x}_i^{G,ATRA} \frac{FTR_i}{\bar{FTR}_i} \left(\frac{p_i^{FTR} \bar{p}^{G,ATRA}}{\bar{p}_i^{FTR} p^{G,ATRA}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{flaw}} + \bar{x}_{ELY_TDT}^{G,ATRA} \frac{ELY_TDT}{\bar{ELY_TDT}} + \sum_{elytec} \bar{x}_{elytec}^{G,ATRA} \frac{x_{elytec}}{\bar{x}_{elytec}} \\
& + \sum_{heatec} \bar{x}_{heatec}^{G,ATRA} \frac{x_{heatec}}{\bar{x}_{heatec}} + \sum_n \bar{x}_n^{G,ATRA} \frac{x_n^{Cog}}{\bar{x}_n^{Cog}} + \bar{x}_{GASS}^{G,ATRA} \frac{x^{GASS}}{\bar{x}^{GASS}} + \bar{x}_{BFB}^{G,ATRA} \frac{x^{BFB}}{\bar{x}^{BFB}} \\
& + \bar{x}_{HDE}^{G,ATRA} \frac{x^{HDE}}{\bar{x}^{HDE}} + \bar{x}_{Th}^{G,ATRA} \frac{Th}{\bar{Th}} + \bar{x}_{Mg}^{G,ATRA} \frac{Mg}{\bar{Mg}} \left(\frac{p^{Mg} \bar{p}^{G,ATRA}}{\bar{p}^{Mg} p^{G,ATRA}} \right)^{\sigma^{nene}} + \bar{x}_{INV}^{G,ATRA} \frac{x^{INV}}{\bar{x}^{INV}}
\end{aligned}$$

The demand equation for all land freight transport sectors (*lft*, including RAILFT, ROADFT) is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_{lft}^G = & \sum_i \bar{x}_i^{G,lft} \frac{OTRA_i}{\overline{OTRA}_i} \left(\frac{p_i^{OTRA} \bar{p}^{G,lft}}{\bar{p}_i^{OTRA} p^{G,lft}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{frrr}} + \bar{x}_{ELY_TDT}^{G,lft} \frac{ELY_TDT}{\overline{ELY_TDT}} + \sum_{elytec} \bar{x}_{elytec}^{G,lft} \frac{x_{elytec}}{\bar{x}_{elytec}} \\
& + \sum_{heatec} \bar{x}_{heatec}^{G,lft} \frac{x_{heatec}}{\bar{x}_{heatec}} + \sum_n \bar{x}_n^{G,lft} \frac{x_n^{Cog}}{\bar{x}_n^{Cog}} + \bar{x}_{GASS}^{G,lft} \frac{x^{GASS}}{\bar{x}^{GASS}} + \bar{x}_{BFB}^{G,lft} \frac{x^{BFB}}{\bar{x}^{BFB}} + \bar{x}_{HDE}^{G,lft} \frac{x^{HDE}}{\bar{x}^{HDE}} \\
& + \bar{x}_{INV}^{G,lft} \frac{x^{INV}}{\bar{x}^{INV}}
\end{aligned}$$

The demand equation for long range land passenger transport services ROADPT and RAILPT is the same.

For simplicity only the equation for ROADPT is shown:

$$x_{ROADPT}^G = \bar{x}_{LONG}^{G,ROADPT} \frac{LONG}{\overline{LONG}} \left(\frac{p^{LONG} \bar{p}^{G,ROADPT}}{\bar{p}^{LONG} p^{G,ROADPT}} \right)^{\sigma^{rora}} + \bar{x}_{Mg}^{G,ROADPT} \frac{Mg}{\overline{Mg}} \left(\frac{p^{Mg} \bar{p}^{G,ROADPT}}{\bar{p}^{Mg} p^{G,ROADPT}} \right)^{\sigma^{nene}}$$

For short range land transport services CITYPT the demand equation is as follows:

$$x_{CITYPT}^G = \bar{x}_{SHRT}^{G,CITYPT} \frac{SHRT}{\overline{SHRT}} \left(\frac{p^{SHRT} \bar{p}^{G,CITYPT}}{\bar{p}^{SHRT} p^{G,CITYPT}} \right)^{\sigma^{city}} + \bar{x}_{Mg}^{G,CITYPT} \frac{Mg}{\overline{Mg}} \left(\frac{p^{Mg} \bar{p}^{G,CITYPT}}{\bar{p}^{Mg} p^{G,CITYPT}} \right)^{\sigma^{nene}}$$

For LTREST the demand equation is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_{LTREST}^G = & \sum_i \bar{x}_i^{G,LTREST} \frac{OTRA_i}{\overline{OTRA}_i} \left(\frac{p_i^{OTRA} \bar{p}^{G,LTREST}}{\bar{p}_i^{OTRA} p^{G,LTREST}} \right)^{\sigma_i^{frrr}} + \bar{x}_{ELY_TDT}^{G,LTREST} \frac{ELY_TDT}{\overline{ELY_TDT}} \\
& + \sum_{elytec} \bar{x}_{elytec}^{G,LTREST} \frac{x_{elytec}}{\bar{x}_{elytec}} + \sum_{heatec} \bar{x}_{heatec}^{G,LTREST} \frac{x_{heatec}}{\bar{x}_{heatec}} + \sum_n \bar{x}_n^{G,LTREST} \frac{x_n^{Cog}}{\bar{x}_n^{Cog}} \\
& + \bar{x}_{GASS}^{G,LTREST} \frac{x^{GASS}}{\bar{x}_{GASS}} + \bar{x}_{BFB}^{G,LTREST} \frac{x^{BFB}}{\bar{x}_{BFB}} + \bar{x}_{HDE}^{G,LTREST} \frac{x^{HDE}}{\bar{x}_{HDE}} \\
& + \bar{x}_{SHRT}^{G,LTREST} \frac{SHRT}{\overline{SHRT}} \left(\frac{p^{SHRT} \bar{p}^{G,LTREST}}{\bar{p}^{SHRT} p^{G,LTREST}} \right)^{\sigma^{city}} + \bar{x}_{Mg}^{G,LTREST} \frac{Mg}{\overline{Mg}} \left(\frac{p^{Mg} \bar{p}^{G,LTREST}}{\bar{p}^{Mg} p^{G,LTREST}} \right)^{\sigma^{nene}} \\
& + \bar{x}_{INV}^{G,LTREST} \frac{x^{INV}}{\bar{x}^{INV}}
\end{aligned}$$

For the transport infrastructure providing sectors, the demand equations are as follows:

$$x_{STREST}^G = \sum_m \bar{x}_m^{G,STREST} \frac{T_m}{\bar{T}_m}$$

with m being all sectors except RAILFT and ROADFT

$$x_{STROAD}^G = \bar{x}_{ROADFT}^{G,STROAD} \frac{T_{ROADFT}}{\bar{T}_{ROADFT}}$$

$$x_{STRAIL}^G = \bar{x}_{RAILFT}^{G,STRAIL} \frac{T_{RAILFT}}{\bar{T}_{RAILFT}}$$

2.3.4. Market clearance for production factors

The production factors capital K , labor L and land LN are supplied at fixed quantities with prices being flexible in order to clear the factor markets.

$$\bar{K} \geq \sum_j \bar{K}_j \frac{KLLN_j}{KLLN_j} \left(\frac{p_j^{KLLN} p^K}{\bar{p}_j^{KLLN} \bar{p}^K} \right)^{\sigma^{kl}}$$

$$\bar{L} \geq \sum_j \bar{L}_j \frac{KLLN_j}{KLLN_j} \left(\frac{p_j^{KLLN} p^L}{\bar{p}_j^{KLLN} \bar{p}^L} \right)^{\sigma^{kl}}$$

$$\bar{LN} \geq \sum_j \bar{LN}_j \frac{KLLN_j}{KLLN_j} \left(\frac{p_j^{KLLN} p^{LN}}{\bar{p}_j^{KLLN} \bar{p}^{LN}} \right)^{\sigma^{kl}}$$

2.3.5. Consumption and investment demand

Consumption (W) and investment (INV) demand by private households are fixed shared of private income (PRI). For the public household there is only demand for consumption ($WGOV$), which is financed out of public income (PUI). The demand equations for W and INV can thus be written as follows, with PRI and PUI constraining final demand and thus overall economic activity:

$$W = \bar{W} \frac{PRI}{\bar{PRI}}$$

$$x^{INV} = \bar{x}^{INV} \frac{PRI}{\bar{PRI}}$$

$$WGOV = \bar{WGOV} \frac{PUI}{\bar{PUI}}$$

2.4. Income balance conditions

2.4.1. Private households

For each private household h income is composed out of factor income (capital, labor, land) and transfers from the public household. Total income is either spent for consumption (W) or is saved. Savings in turn determine investment. The income balance and the budget constraint for private households is thus formulated as follows:

$$PRI = p^K \bar{K} + p^L \bar{L} + p^{LN} \bar{LN} + \overline{TRANS} = p^W W + p^{INV} x^{INV}$$

2.4.2. Public household

The public household generates public income (PUI) out of ad valorem taxes on capital, labor and land, using fixed tax rates t . Also, there are taxes levied on production output X , as well as on private and public consumption (W and $WGOV$) and investments. The income balance and budget constraint are thus formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} PUI &= p^K \bar{K} \bar{t}^K + p^L \bar{L} \bar{t}^L + p^{LN} \bar{LN} \bar{t}^{LN} + \sum_i p_i^X x_i^X \bar{t}^x + p^W W \bar{t}^W + p^{WGOV} WGOV \bar{t}^{WGOV} + p^{INV} x^{INV} \bar{t}^{INV} \\ &= p^{WGOV} WGOV + \overline{TRANS} \end{aligned}$$

2.5. Model closures

Government balance: The government balance is closed via fixed tax rates. Thus, the tax base is flexible and determines via fixed tax rates the tax income of the government.

Savings-Investment balance: The savings-investment balance is closed via flexible savings, which are a fixed share of private income, which in turn determined investment demand.

Balance of payments: The balance of payments is closed via a fixed current account a flexible exchange rate.

3. Recursive dynamics and growth

WEGDYN-AT is a recursive dynamic model. This means that annual equilibria are connected via capital accumulation over time. The capital stock KS of the next period $t + 1$ is determined by the current year t capital stock and its depreciation ($\delta = 5\%$), plus investments of the current period:

$$KS_{t+1} = KS_t(1 - \delta) + x_t^{INV}$$

The relative capital growth rate between the two periods then is applied to the capital endowment of the economy. As already explained, the total amount of investment is determined via a fixed savings rate, which means that a fixed share of income is devoted to savings/investment. There is no forward-looking behavior and agents are assumed to behave myopic.

In addition to growth via capital accumulation, there is also growth via an increasing population and thus labor supply. The labor endowment is assumed to grow moderately at an exogenously fixed growth rate of 0.175% per year.

Next to the growth of factor endowments, there is also a generic exogenous autonomous energy efficiency (AEEI = 3% p.a.) parameter, which is multiplied to the share parameter θ in the production functions at every instance where an energy input is used. This means that over time the requirement for energy is being reduced “autonomously” (at no costs) and that the same output can be produced at lower input requirements. Next to the generic AEEI, there is also a specific parameter for the autonomous cost digression of the two electricity generation technologies wind and photovoltaics, with respective annual cost reduction of 1.5% and 2%. This cost digression is implemented in terms of lower intermediate demand at constant output in the production of wind power (WI_ely) and electricity from photovoltaics (PV_ely).

Finally, to endogenously calibrate Austria’s GDP growth to an exogenously given growth rate (1.65% p.a.), the TFP parameter adjust endogenously such that the required GDP is met. The TFP parameter is multiplied to all factor endowments. This means that for factors there are two components for growth: first, a quantity

fraction (given by the capital growth or labor growth factor) and second the productivity growth factor TFP.

Note that for land we assume the same growth rate as for capital.

4. Benchmark data and calibration

4.1. Overview

WEGDYN-AT is calibrated to a social accounting matrix (SAM) which is based on the input output (IO) table provided by Statistics Austria (2014). The SAM is extended as follows: The land transport and energy sectors are further disaggregated to integrate technological detail. Further, the representative private household is split into twelve different household groups, enabling the analysis of distributional effects. CO₂ emissions are added to production and final demand. The following sub-sections provide a detailed description of these extensions.

4.2. Production sectors

Table 1 shows the 81 production sectors with corresponding NACE code (ÖNACE 2008 / NACE Rev. 2.1 classification) and a brief description (for the respective production functions and nesting trees see sections 0 and 2) as well as an attribution to sector aggregates which are sometimes used for presentation of results and data. The model itself solves for each of the sectors as given in the column “Model sector” in Table 1. In WEGDYN-AT special emphasis is placed on the land transport and energy sector, which are described in more detail in the ongoing sub-sections.

Table 1: Overview of production sectors in WEGDYN-AT.

Model sector	NACE code	Description	Aggregate
AGRI	A 01	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	AGFO
FORE	A 02	Forestry and logging	
FISC	A 03	Fishing and aquaculture	
FEXT	B 05-07; C 19	Mining of coal and lignite; Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas; Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products	FMRO
MEXT	B 08-09	Other mining and quarrying	MANU
FOOD	C 10	Manufacture of food products	
BEVE	C 11 - C 12	Manufacture of beverages	

Model sector	NACE code	Description	Aggregate	
TEXT	C 13	Manufacture of textiles		
CLOT	C 14	Manufacture of wearing apparel		
LEAT	C 15	Manufacture of leather and related products		
WOOD	C 16	Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials		
PAPE	C 17	Manufacture of paper and paper products		
PRNT	C 18	Printing and reproduction of recorded media		
CHEM	C 20	Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products		
PHAM	C 21	Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations		
PLAS	C 22	Manufacture of rubber and plastic products		
GLAS	C 23	Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products		
META	C 24	Manufacture of basic metals		
MAME	C 25	Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment		
MAED	C 26	Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products		
MAEL	C 27	Manufacture of electrical equipment		
MACA	C 28	Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c.		
MAVE	C 29	Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers		
MAVO	C 30	Manufacture of other transport equipment		
MAFU	C 31	Manufacture of furniture		
MAOT	C 32	Other manufacturing		
MARE	C 33	Repair and installation of machinery and equipment		
ELYS	D 35	Electricity supply		ENER
HEATS		Heat supply		
GASS		Natural gas supply		
WATE	E 36	Water collection, treatment and supply	WAWA	
WAST	E 37-39	Rest of E		
BUIL	F 41	Construction of buildings	CONS	
CIEN	F 42	Civil engineering		
CONT	F 43	Specialised construction activities		
TRCA	G 45	Wholesale and retail trade and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	TRADE	
TRWH	G 46	Wholesale trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles		
TRRE	G 47	Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles		

Model sector	NACE code	Description	Aggregate
RAILPT	H 49	Rail passenger transport	LTRA
RAILFT		Rail freight transport	
ROADPT		Road passenger transport	
CITYPT		City passenger transport	
ROADFT		Road freight transport	
LTrest		Land transport rest	
WTRA	H 50	Water transport	WATR
ATRA	H 51	Air transport	
STRAIL	H 52	Warehousing and support activities for rail transportation	SERV
STROAD		Warehousing and support activities for road transportation	
STREST		Warehousing and support activities for other transportation	
POST	H 53	Postal and courier activities	
ACCO	I 55-56	Accommodation and food service activities	
SPUB	J 58	Publishing activities	
CINE	J 59	Motion picture, video and television programme production, sound recording and music publishing activities	
BRDC	J 60	Programming and broadcasting activities	
TELE	J 61	Telecommunications	
SITC	J 62-63	Computer programming, consultancy and related activities; Information service activities	
SFIN	K 64	Financial service activities, except insurance and pension funding	
INPE	K 65	Insurance, reinsurance and pension funding, except compulsory social security	
SFIO	K 66	Activities auxiliary to financial services and insurance activities	
REAL	L 68	Real estate activities	
LEGA	M 69	Legal and accounting activities	
CNSU	M 70	Activities of head offices; management consultancy activities	
ARCH	M 71	Architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis	
RADE	M 72	Scientific research and development	
ADVT	M 73	Advertising and market research	
FREO	M 74-75	Other professional, scientific and technical activities; Veterinary activities	

Model sector	NACE code	Description	Aggregate
SRNT	N 77	Rental and leasing activities	
SLAB	N 78	Employment activities	
TRAV	N 79	Travel agency, tour operator and other reservation service and related activities	
SECO	N 80-82	Rest of N	
PUBL	O 84	Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	
EDUC	P 85	Education	
HEAL	Q 86	Human health activities	
NURS	Q 87-88	Residential care activities; Social work activities without accommodation	
ARTS	R 90	Creative, arts and entertainment activities	
CULT	R 91	Libraries, archives, museums and other cultural activities	
GMBL	R 92	Gambling and betting activities	
SPOR	R 93	Sports activities and amusement and recreation activities	
ASSO	S 94	Activities of membership organisations	
UREP	S 95	Repair of computers and personal and household goods	
SOTH	S 96	Other personal service activities	

4.2.1. The land transport sector

The land transport sector (NACE code H 49) of the original IO table is disaggregated and incorporates six transport service subsectors, which represent different technologies: rail passenger transport, rail freight transport, road passenger transport, road freight transport, city passenger transport as well as rest of land transport. In addition, there are three sub-sectors, which cover support services for transportation (i.e. providing infrastructure for rail transport, road transport, and remaining service activities for land transport) based on (EUROSTAT, 2020). The exact procedure of the disaggregation of the land transport sector is described in Bachner (2017).

4.2.2. The energy supply sector

The energy sector (NACE code D 35) comprises subsectors electricity supply (35.1), gas supply (35.2) and heating and cooling supply (35.3). The original energy sector is disaggregated using bottom-up information of MWh (Statistics Austria, 2014b) in energy supply from the Austrian energy balance (see Figure 15), combined with levelized cost of energy assumptions taken from Alberici et al. (2014), Fallmann et al. (2015) and Hansen (2019). This gives subsector turnovers, for which we use structural business statistics by (EUROSTAT, 2020) to allocate commodity and factor inputs, respectively. This results in an energy supply mix, which is composed out of the following eight electricity generation technologies: Coal, Oil, Gas, Waste, Biomass, Hydropower, Wind power as well as Photovoltaics. Additionally, there are five co-generation (cog) technologies, which supply both electricity and heat: Coal-cog, Oil-cog, Gas-cog, Waste-cog, Biomass-cog. Finally, there are seven technologies that produce only heat: Oil-heat, Gas-heat, Waste-heat, Biomass-heat, Geothermal-heat, Solar-heat, Other-heat. All other energy related sectors are specified as given in the original IO table by Statistics Austria (2014a) and not further disaggregated. For the exact specification in terms of production functions see section 2.

Figure 15: Austrian electricity and heat supply 2014 (Statistics Austria, 2014b).

4.2.3. The metals sector

To account for the importance of the iron and steel sector and its CO₂ emissions in Austria, the NACE sector C24 “Manufacture of basic metals” is split into a fraction that captures the blast-furnace basic-oxygen-furnace production route of crude steel as well as a “rest of metals” sector, which captures the downstream processing of crude steel into final steel. This split allows for modelling a direct substitution of crude steel production processes, for example by a hydrogen-based production technology. The split is done using cost structures as described in Mayer et al. (2019).

4.3. Final demand

The final demand side is split between (private and public) consumption, investments and foreign trade. Public consumption, economy-wide investment as well as foreign trade is used in the same way as provided by Statistics Austria (2014a), whereas the final demand (and income) structure for the private household in WEGDYN-AT is disaggregated to be able to study distributional effects of system interventions.

4.3.1. Private households

4.3.1.1. Private household groups

Regarding private households we disaggregate the single representative private household of the original IO table (i.e. the national account) into twelve heterogeneous household groups, distinguished by income quartiles and three different locations of residence (urban [Vienna plus municipalities with more than 100 thousand inhabitants], suburban [municipalities between 10 and 100 thousand inhabitants] and peripheral regions [municipalities with less than 10 thousand inhabitants]). Table 2 shows the exact numbers of people in each of the twelve household groups.

Table 2: Number of people (thousands) in household groups based on Statistics Austria (2014c).

Residence location		Income quartile				
		Total	Q1 (low)	Q2	Q3	Q4 (high)
Urban	Vienna plus municipalities >100k inhab.	2,301	723	510	515	553
Suburban	Municipalities >10k and ≤100k inhab.	1,339	325	326	340	349
Periphery	Municipalities ≤10k inhab.	4,830	1,071	1,282	1,262	1,216
Total		8,469	2,118	2,117	2,117	2,117
<i>Note: Differences are due to rounding.</i>						

4.3.1.2. Expenditure side of households

The expenditure structure of the representative private household from the Austrian national account is disentangled in several steps. First, household group specific consumption patterns are obtained from the Austrian household budget survey (HBS; Statistics Austria, 2014c). In a second step, the HBS data across household groups is scaled to match the consumption vector given in the national account while maintaining group-specific consumption patterns. This results in twelve consumption vectors C_h (net of taxes) for private household groups h that in sum match with the total consumption as given in the national accounts. In the next step, again scaling the data to match the national account where necessary, we compute disposable

income Y_h on the basis of its relationship with current consumption C_h and observed savings rate sr_h (based on Fessler and Schürz (2017):

$$Y_h = \frac{C_h}{(1 - sr_h)}$$

Figure 16 shows the resulting structure in terms of consumption and savings relations for the representative private agent (as given in the IO table), the twelve individual private households groups after disaggregation (which in sum again give the RA), as well as the public expenditure split between consumption and transfers (no public investment is assumed).

Figure 16: Expenditure (i.e. income use) for the representative agents (RA), across the twelve private households groups (left panel) and the public household (right panel).

The household-specific consumption vectors for groups of households are characterized such that the share of energy-related expenses (heating, cooling and other uses but excluding transport, reflected by the commodity bundle “FMRO+ENER” in Figure 17) declines with rising income level and rising degree of urbanization. For transport (including land, water and air), a higher share of expenses for households living in peripheral regions and high-income levels becomes visible.

Based on the household budget survey, land passenger transport is divided into conventional motorized individual transport (cMIT) and public transport, which differentiates rail passenger (RailPT), road passenger (RoadPT) and short-distance urban (CityPT) as well as other means of transport e.g., taxis (LTrest). Figure 18 shows that there are higher shares of expenses for public transportation in urban regions as well as for low(er) income groups.

Figure 17: Structure of private consumption vectors (by sector aggregates as explained in Table 1).

Figure 18: Share of technology-specific expenses in land transport demand across groups of private households; cMIT... conventional motorized individual transport, PT... passenger transport.

4.3.1.3. Income side of households

For the income side, factor remuneration (i.e. labor and capital income, net of taxes) is allocated across private household groups based on data of the EU survey on income and living conditions (EU-SILC; Statistics Austria, 2014d) and scaled such that the sum over all household groups matches the national

account. To close the household account, the structure of transfers from the public to the private household is derived as the residual between disposable income and factor remuneration. In total, transfers to private households match with numbers given in the national account.

The corresponding income distribution and structure of household group-specific sources of income is shown in Figure 19, which shows that the share of labor income versus capital income is larger for low-income households (Q1) across residence locations. Furthermore, the share of transfer income decreases with income levels. For the richest quartile, net transfers are even negative, which means that these household groups transfer parts of their income indirectly to other groups in the society, because the tax burden of these groups is higher than received social payments such as child care benefits.

Figure 19: Sources of income for the representative private agent (RA), across the twelve private household groups (left panel) and the public household (right panel). *labor taxes include social contributions.

4.3.2. The public household

For public consumption, a single public household collects taxes, gives transfers and subsidies and creates provision of public goods and services (via public consumption). The share of income sources and uses for the public household are shown in Figure 16 and Figure 19 (right panels). Average tax rates in the SAM are 43% for the category “labor taxes and social contributions”, 12% for “capital taxes” and 4% for “commodity

taxes, excise duties and subsidies.” In the underlying SAM, a substantial share (48%) of the public budget is transferred to private households and the remaining share is spent for provision of public goods and services in terms of public consumption. Note that public consumption of around 65 Bn. EUR makes up around 25% of benchmark economy-wide consumption. Around two thirds of public consumption are devoted to provision of merit goods and services such as education, health and social security.

4.4. CO₂ emissions

WEGDYN-AT explicitly considers CO₂ emissions (no other greenhouse gases). Statistics Austria (2014b) provides the relevant data structured by production and consumption activities based on a NACE-sector-classified distribution. Furthermore, the model distinguishes between CO₂ emissions that are regulated via the EU Emission Trading System (ETS) and other non-ETS emissions (Abrell et al., 2022), allowing for modelling different price settings or cap-and-trade policies for ETS and non-ETS emissions. Next to combustion-based emissions also industrial process emissions are covered, based on UNFCCC emission inventories.

Figure 20 gives an overview of CO₂ emissions in Austria for the benchmark year 2014. Total verified ETS emissions allocated in the SAM for Austria in 2014 amount to around 28 MtCO₂ and non-ETS emissions around 33 MtCO₂ from which around 19 MtCO₂ accrue in the intermediate demand structure of production activities. The remaining 14 MtCO₂ of non-ETS emissions concern transport- (7.5 MtCO₂) and energy-related expenses for heating/cooling (5.6 MtCO₂) and other uses (0.9 MtCO₂) in final demand.

Figure 20: Overview of CO₂ emissions in 2014 in Austria.

4.5. Elasticities of substitution

Table 3: Elasticities of substitution in production

Elasticity of substitution (σ)	kl	kle	int	top	armi	frrr
Source	Okagawa and Ban (2008)		(Hertel et al. (2014))		(Puwein, 2009)	
Definition	capital-labor	kl-energy	intermediate	top	armington	freight rail-road-rest
AGRI	0.023	0.516	0	0.392	3.050	0.700
FORE	0.087	0.456	0.115	0.695	2.500	0
FISC	0.023	0.516	0	0.392	1.900	0.550
FEXT	0.139	0.553	0.309	0.729	5.520	0.350
MEXT	0.139	0.553	0.309	0.729	5.520	1.850
FOOD	0.382	0.395	0	0.329	1.900	0.550
BEVE	0.382	0.395	0	0.329	1.100	0.700
TEXT	0.161	0.637	0.597	0.722	3.300	0.400
CLOT	0.161	0.637	0.597	0.722	3.300	0.400
LEAT	0.161	0.637	0.597	0.722	1.900	0.700
WOOD	0.087	0.456	0.115	0.695	4.400	0
PAPE	0.381	0.211	0	0.187	3.000	1.650
PRNT	0.381	0.211	0	0.187	3.300	0.700
CHEM	0.334	0	0.082	0.848	3.300	1.000
PHAM	0.334	0	0.082	0.848	3.300	0.700
PLAS	0.334	0	0.082	0.848	1.900	1.650
GLAS	0.358	0.411	0.191	0.306	3.300	1.850
META	0.220	0.644	0.253	1.173	2.200	1.300
MAME	0.220	0.644	0.253	1.173	1.900	1.300
MAED	0.163	0.524	0.359	0.876	3.300	0.700
MAEL	0.163	0.524	0.359	0.876	1.900	0.700
MACA	0.046	0.529	0.309	0.406	4.000	1.100
MAVE	0.046	0.529	0.309	0.406	1.900	0.500
MAVO	0.046	0.529	0.309	0.406	1.900	0.500
MAFU	0.046	0.529	0.309	0.406	3.300	0.700
MAOT	0.046	0.529	0.309	0.406	3.300	0.700
MARE	0.046	0.529	0.309	0.406	3.300	0.700
ELYs	0.460	0.256	0.391	0	2.800	0.700
HEATs	0.460	0.256	0.391	0	2.800	0.700
GAS_MDT	0.460	0.256	0.391	0	2.800	0.700
WATE	0.460	0.256	0.391	0	2.800	0.700
WAST	0.460	0.256	0.391	0	1.900	0.700
BUIL	0.065	0.529	0	1.264	1.900	0.700
CIEN	0.065	0.529	0	1.264	1.900	0.700
CONT	0.065	0.529	0	1.264	1.900	0.700

Elasticity of substitution (σ)	kl	kle	int	top	armi	frrr
Source	Okagawa and Ban (2008)		(Hertel et al. (2014))		(Puwein, 2009)	
Definition	capital-labor	kl-energy	intermediate	top	armington	freight rail-road-rest
TRCA	0.310	0.281	0.331	0.352	1.900	0.700
TRWH	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
TRRE	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
RAILPT	0.310	0.281	0.331	0.352	1.900	0.700
RAILFT	0.310	0.281	0.331	0.352	1.900	0.700
ROADPT	0.310	0.281	0.331	0.352	1.900	0.700
CITYPT	0.310	0.281	0.331	0.352	1.900	0.700
ROADFT	0.310	0.281	0.331	0.352	1.900	0.700
LTrest	0.310	0.281	0.331	0.352	1.900	0.700
WTRA	0.310	0.281	0.331	0.352	1.900	0.700
ATRA	0.310	0.281	0.331	0.352	1.900	0.700
STRAIL	0.144	0.519	1.087	0.548	1.900	0.700
STROAD	0.144	0.519	1.087	0.548	1.900	0.700
STREST	0.144	0.519	1.087	0.548	1.900	0.700
POST	0.370	0.518	0.711	0.654	1.900	0.700
ACCO	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
SPUB	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
CINE	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
BRDC	0.370	0.518	0.711	0.654	1.900	0.700
TELE	0.370	0.518	0.711	0.654	1.900	0.700
SITC	0.370	0.518	0.711	0.654	1.900	0.700
SFIN	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
INPE	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
SFIO	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
REAL	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
LEGA	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
CNSU	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
ARCH	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
RADE	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
ADVT	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
FREO	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
SRNT	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
SLAB	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
TRAV	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
SECO	0.264	0.320	0	0.492	1.900	0.700
PUBL	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
EDUC	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
HEAL	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700

Elasticity of substitution (σ)	kl	kle	int	top	armi	frrr
Source	Okagawa and Ban (2008)		(Hertel et al. (2014))		(Puwein, 2009)	
Definition	capital-labor	kl-energy	intermediate	top	armington	freight rail-road-rest
NURS	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
ARTS	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
CULT	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
GMBL	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
SPOR	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
ASSO	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
UREP	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700
SOTH	0.316	0.784	0.132	0.902	1.900	0.700

Table 4: Elasticities of substitution in consumption.

		Elasticity of substitution (σ)				
		city	rora	pult	mipu	plaw
Source:		Puwein (2009)				
Residence location	Income quartile	intra-urban	inter-urban rail-road	long-short distance	moto-indiv/public	land-air-water
Urban	Q1	0.100	0.440	0	0.422	0
	Q2	0.100	0.440	0	0.290	0
	Q3	0.100	0.440	0	0.250	0
	Q4	0.100	0.440	0	0.164	0
Suburban	Q1	0.100	0.440	0	0.117	0
	Q2	0.100	0.440	0	0.124	0
	Q3	0.100	0.440	0	0.210	0
	Q4	0.100	0.440	0	0.050	0
Periphery	Q1	0.100	0.440	0	0.514	0
	Q2	0.100	0.440	0	0.164	0
	Q3	0.100	0.440	0	0.050	0
	Q4	0.100	0.440	0	0.050	0

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